

METHODS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STUDY OF THE TOPIC OF THE MAIN PARTS OF THE SENTENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8188358>

ANNOTATION: This article talks about the effective aspects and practical results of using information communication tools in teaching elementary school students about the topic of the main parts of the sentence in the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy. As an example, it was given how to teach in the section of classes.

KEY WORDS: technology, educational system, efficiency, skill, skill, competence, pedagogy, innovation, innovation, integration.

According to the Ministry of Public Education, the total number of primary school students in our republic is 2,129,389. 111866 pedagogues have been teaching them. Currently, our state takes the necessary measures to ensure that teachers have a creative approach to lessons, to widely introduce advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies to their activities, and to strengthen the foundation of students' initial knowledge acquisition, and to increase their interest in mastering all subjects. activities are developed and implemented.

The current period places great demands on the teacher and the student, the most important of these demands are the effectiveness of the lesson, its quality, the knowledge and skills of the students, various educational activities in schools, their organization and through it students acquire various knowledge and skills. Today, the role of innovative technologies, technical tools, including modern computers, in the correct and effective organization of the educational process is incomparable. The use of multimedia, animation, graphics, slide films and video films on the subject of the lesson helps to make the lesson process more interesting, and for this, the teacher can work on himself and start each lesson with "what is new about today's lesson process?" come in and make the lesson interesting he should ask himself the question, that is, he should avoid traditional education and try to provide non-traditional education.

It is known that education is a type of activity in cooperation between the teacher and the students. as a result of receiving it, he will have the competencies to use it. In the process of learning new knowledge, students naturally use different forms of learning, such as receiving information, processing it, and putting it into practice.

Nowadays, it is no secret to anyone that advanced pedagogic scientists recognize that one of the most important indicators is the improvement of the possibilities of using modern computer technologies in general education schools, the full use of the possibilities of modern technologies in the educational process. In particular, U.Sh. Begimkulov suggests the creation of a computer information environment that can meet the requirements of the present time in

the educational process, as well as the creation of a recommended database for multimedia in the educational process, imitation in teaching, input, systematization, storage and use of the necessary information with the help of computer technology.

Almost all secondary schools in our country are equipped with modern computer and telecommunication technologies. This, in turn, requires primary school teachers to have a new approach to their work. The introduction of new technologies into the educational process of elementary school classes, not to squeeze the teacher by technical means, but to change his task and role through a new approach, based on a more lively, creative and creative approach to teaching activities. turns into a profession.

When organizing the lesson process with the help of modern information technologies, the teacher should first:

- the purpose of the lesson;
- ways to achieve the goal;
- methods of presenting educational materials;
 - teaching methods;
- types of educational assignments;
 - questions for discussion;
- ways of organizing discussions and debates;
- it is necessary to identify factors such as methods of interaction and communication.

In the process of education, in the process of raising students to be intellectually and spiritually mature people, knowledge about the essence of our national traditions and values, the use of computer and information technologies plays an important role in learning the rich spiritual heritage of our great ancestors while developing their skills and abilities. Pedagogical staff and students will have the opportunity to receive, search, process and master a large amount of information through computer and information technology tools. Of course, introduction of new pedagogical and information technologies in educational institutions. Conducting training sessions using new interactive methods, modern tools, i.e. information technology tools, including the use of multimedia in classes, the Internet^{54\9}

Using it will definitely have its effect.

By using modern computer technologies, the teacher can perform the following tasks:

- students' interest in science develops through the use of multimedia technologies in elementary grades;
- this method of education activates students' thinking abilities and increases the efficiency of learning material;
- provides an opportunity to model and visualize processes that are difficult or complex to demonstrate;
- assimilation of educational materials is effective not only according to the level, but also according to the level of logic and acceptance of students;
- students are given the opportunity to search for and find materials and find answers to problematic issues through independent research;
- conditions are created for students to master a new topic, solve examples, write essays, reports, get acquainted with educational materials, select and analyze information and data quickly.

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in

traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the acquired knowledge themselves, independently study and think, analyze, and even finalize the acquired knowledge. teaches them to make their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

Applying modern information technologies to primary education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also plays an important role in educating an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded and highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice.

Every teacher should be creative, he should enter every lesson thoroughly prepared and innovative, because the sameness repeated in every lesson weakens the student's interest in the lesson and science, as a result, it leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the lesson.

Important aspects of information technology for the teacher and student are as follows:

- ☒ concentration of the student's attention;
- ☒ expand the perception of information; ☒ inquiry, creativity and independent activity;
- ☒ self-assessment.

The role of lessons using information technologies in the teacher's activity is reflected in the following:

- ☒ proper distribution of time;
- ☒ to ensure that the content of the educational material is bright and convincing;
- ☒ increase the amount of information provided;
- ☒ expanding the types of educational tasks;
- ☒ creation of healthy competition, creative environment;
- ☒ regular improvement of professional qualifications.

Computer software can be used to prepare simple didactic materials and present them to students for independent work in computer classes. Such didactic material is given to students in the form of an explanatory text, decorated with pictures, with control questions, and their performance is monitored.

One of the most important aspects of a teacher's work is to evaluate the knowledge of students. Control tests for various departments of all general education subjects can be created using a computer.

Today, a special market of programs used as a didactic tool in the educational process is forming in Uzbekistan. There are many programs available online that can be used in general education classes. First of all, electronic textbooks can be included among these. Computer technologies provide the opportunity to use various interactive tasks. For example, students can arrange events in chronological order, correctly explain scientific terms and concepts, or indicate the terms and their meanings in the right and left rows with an arrow, or correct key words in the given topic. they will be able to find out how they performed tasks such as reading, completing test tasks, solving crosswords, comparing them with the answers displayed on the big screen using multimedia. During the lesson, the teacher uses the computer to present the existing materials in various forms: slides, video and audio clips, diagrams, tables, and musical forms. The organization of the lesson process with the help of a computer has a strong effect on the imagination and memory of students, facilitates the

process of remembering, turns the lesson into an interesting process, allows students to take part in one or another historical period and participate in the events.

Today's education requires the teacher to use advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. We present our thoughts and opinions on education by using interactive methods in the lessons. We present our thoughts on the implementation of modern methods of teaching on the basis of certain topics in primary classes.

"Video find" method - the following sequence of actions should be performed when using this method:

- several video clips are shown to the attention of students without comments, which help to illustrate the essence of the topic being studied;
- students explain what process is shown in each picture;
- record the nature of the processes in their notebooks;
- answer the questions asked by the teacher.

Based on this method, a video on the topic is shown through a computer. Students express their opinions about the topic of the video and the topic expressed in it.

In conclusion, the use of modern information and communication technologies in primary grades helps students to think independently, expand their creative research and logical thinking, connect what they learned in lessons with life, and increase their interest in the lesson. The effective use of conditions created by teachers based on such modern requirements and the organization of classes based on advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies guarantees the quality of the educational process.

It is worth saying that as a result of using multimedia applications in every lesson, students' independent and creative thinking develops even more. As a conclusion, it can be said that the use of information and communication tools in primary school classes serves to increase the quality and efficiency of the lesson.

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